

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF PULTRUDED FIBER-POLYMER COMPOSITES

Gisele G. Cintra, Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, giselegoes.c@gmail.com

Janine D. Vieira, Fluminense Federal University, janinedv@id.uff.br

Daniel C.T. Cardoso, Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, dctcardoso@puc-rio.br

Thomas Keller, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, thomas.keller@epfl.ch

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to provide interlaminar fracture mechanics data for pultruded glass fiber-polymer materials, extracted from a composite bridge deck system. Both Modes I and II were investigated, through the adaptation of classical fracture mechanics tests to pultruded specimens. In all, nine data reduction methods were used to determine the Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR) in both Modes and, apart from the Compliance Calibration and Simple Beam Theory methods recommended by current standards, exhibited good agreement between themselves.

KEYWORDS

Pultruded glass fiber-polymer composites; Delamination, Interlaminar fracture.

INTRODUCTION

Despite the significant amount of research conducted in the recent decades on pultruded glass fiber-polymer composites, there are still few fracture mechanics data related to the material in the literature, which hampers the investigations on the failure behavior of these composites. For instance, in order to achieve reliable numerical results, it is often required to conduct an extensive experimental investigation to obtain the concerned composite's fracture parameters. Moreover, the fact that classical fracture mechanics tests are usually performed after introducing a pre-crack in the specimens during their fabrication also contributes to the scarcity of data in the literature, since this procedure is not applicable for pultruded fiber-polymer composites due to their automatic manufacturing process.

Due to the relevance to understand the fracture behavior and obtain the delamination toughness, different experimental methods have been standardized for this purpose, among which one may cite the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) and the End-Loaded-Split (ELS). To the best of the authors' knowledge, with exception of the studies addressing the delamination in adhesively bonded joints, no experimental investigations about the interlaminar fracture of pultruded fiber-polymers have been carried out previously. The few experimental investigations about the fracture behavior of pultruded fiber-polymer materials that can be found in the literature are focused on intralaminar and translaminar fracture, *e.g.* (Almeida-Fernandes, Correia, et al., 2020; Almeida-Fernandes, Silvestre, et al., 2020a; Haj-Ali & El-Hajjar, 2003)

In the numerical field, the cohesive zone model (CZM) is a very powerful tool to predict the onset and progressive failure of composite materials. The cohesive element behavior is defined by a traction-separation law that correlates the surface tractions, σ , with the crack opening displacements (COD), along the fracture process zone (FPZ) of an interfacial crack. A wide variety of studies have shown that the traction-separation law shape is determinant when simulating progressive damage for different materials. Different shapes, such as triangular, trapezoidal, and cubic forms, among others have been proposed in literature. However, the determination of its respective parameters still constitutes a challenge for an accurate numerical analysis, especially when it comes to Mode II.

The limited number of studies available, especially related to the interlaminar fracture and to Mode II, added to the complexity in obtaining fracture parameters, and the well-known high variability observed in general properties in this type of material are aggravating factors that increase the need of reliable guidelines for the accurate determination of fracture characteristics for this material. Moreover, the lack of fracture parameters data for pultruded glass fiber-polymers in literature is a relevant obstacle for appropriate numerical damage simulations, which often cause researchers to adopt properties

without an experimental basis (Almeida-Fernandes, Silvestre, et al., 2020b). Numerically, despite the several studies addressing CZM for fiber-polymer materials, very few studies are focused on the interlaminar fracture behavior characterization of pultruded fiber-polymers, *e.g.* (Almeida-Fernandes, Silvestre, et al., 2020a; Shahverdi et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2010).

Against this background, this work aims to complement the scarcity of the interlaminar fracture data in pultruded glass fiber-polymer composites. Standardized experimental procedures for both Mode I and Mode II were adapted to be applied in pultruded specimens. The starter crack required to perform the classical fracture experiments was introduced via a water jet machine. In all, nine different methods were applied to obtain the Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR) for both Modes.

DATA REDUCTION METHODS - THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

SERR in Mode I

Based on the energy balance approach in the Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) field, Eq. 1 expresses the Irwin-Kies formula, which serves as the basis of measurement of the fracture energy (Bazant, Z. P., & Cedolin, 2010), used in this work as a synonym for fracture toughness or critical SERR.

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where P is the applied load, b is the specimen's width, a is the delamination or crack length measured from the loading line and C is the compliance known as the ratio of δ/P , in which δ is the applied displacement.

Standard methods for the G calculation were derived from this relation, presenting differences basically in the determination of the derivate of dC/da (Zhang et al., 2010). The standard *ASTM D5528-01* (ASTM, 2019) presents three different methods in order to quantify the strain energy released rate (SERR) for Mode I: *i. Modified Beam Theory (MBT)*, *ii. Compliance Calibration (CC)* and *iii. Modified Compliance Calibration (MCC)* methods. The formulae used for each method are expressed in Eqs. from 2 to 4.

$$\text{MBT}_{ASTM} \text{ method} \quad G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\text{CC}_{ASTM} \text{ method} \quad G_I = \frac{nP\delta}{2ba} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\text{MCC}_{ASTM} \text{ method} \quad G_I = \frac{3P^2 C^{2/3}}{2A_1 b h} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where δ is the displacement correspondent to the applied load P and h is the specimen thickness. The parameter Δ expressed in Eq. 2 is an attempt to correct a possible overestimation of G_I due to rotations that may occur at the delamination front (Hashemi S, Kinloch AJ, 1990). Whereas the parameter n of Eq. 3 represents the slope of the logarithmic functions of the compliance ($\log C$) and the delamination length ($\log a$) plotted against each other ($\log C$ vs. $\log a$). Finally, in Eq. 4, the parameter A_1 indicates the slope of the curve (a/h) vs. ($C^{1/3}$).

The standardized MBT_{ASTM} method derives from the elementary beam theory, with the addition of the correction parameter Δ . However, for a crack occurring out of the specimen midplane, this formulation might be inaccurate. To consider the asymmetry generated in this scenario, Mollón *et al.* (Mollón et al., 2010) presented a formulation to determine G_I based on an equivalent stiffness EI_{eq} , as follows:

$$\text{MBT-}EI_{eq} \text{ method} \quad G_I = \frac{3P^2(a + |\Delta|)^2}{2b(EI_{eq})} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where $(1/EI_{eq})^{1/3}$ is the slope of the plot $C^{1/3}$ vs. a .

Regarding the CC method, an alternative function, expressed in Eq. 6, is adopted in some works (Dávila et al., 2009; Laffan et al., 2010) to describe the compliance of compact tension (CT) specimens. The critical SERR in Mode I can be obtained by Eq. 7 and is dependent on the optically measured crack length. Hereafter, the method in which the presented expressions are used will be designated as CC-f method.

$$\text{CC-f method} \quad C = (\alpha a + \beta)^\chi \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2b} \alpha \chi (\alpha a + \beta)^{\chi-1} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

The parameters α , β and χ are the constants calculated to best fit the experimental data.

Likewise, the standardized MCC_{ASTM} method also requires the visual crack length determination in DCB tests. However, to eliminate this optical measurement dependency, an effective crack length a_{eff} – see Eq. 8 – can be determined as a function of the measured compliance presented in Eq. 6. The critical SERR G_{Ic} can also be expressed according to Eq. 7. This procedure is adopted in many works (Almeida-Fernandes et al., 2019; Almeida-Fernandes, Correia, et al., 2020; Bergan et al., 2016; Laffan et al., 2010) and is considered by some authors as the most appropriate data reduction scheme for determining the critical SERR (Laffan et al., 2010). However, it requires additional experiments and increase the complexity in obtaining the compliance vs delamination length curves by numerical simulations (Laffan et al., 2010).

$$\text{MCC-}a_{eff} \text{ method} \quad a_{eff} = \frac{C^{1/\chi} - \beta}{\alpha} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

More conservative G_c values have been found for the MCC- a_{eff} method when compared to CC-f and another popular approach known as J-integral, which accounts for nonlinearities within the fracture process zone (FPZ) at the crack tip (Almeida-Fernandes et al., 2019; Bergan et al., 2016). On the other hand, some authors have observed that although the MCC- a_{eff} method is able to provide a good response for the cohesive behavior, being well correlated with the J-integral, the former is slightly less accurate than the latter. In P vs. δ curves obtained from FEM analyses, the MCC- a_{eff} has underestimated the peak load by 6.9% and overpredicted the critical SERR for propagation by 2% (Bergan et al., 2016). In this context, Almeida-Fernandes (Almeida-Fernandes, Correia, et al., 2020) stated that the method significantly underestimated the critical SERR when compared to other methods, such as J-Integral and CC-f. This fact was attributed to the influence of fiber pull-out in loading/unloading cycles, as well as to the thickness of specimens. However, the MCC- a_{eff} method has the advantage of being simpler since it is based on LEFM conditions. In this work, in an attempt to maintain the simplicity and accuracy for obtaining the SERR parameters of pultruded glass fiber-polymer specimens, six methods based on LEFM are assessed and discussed, among which three are standardized (MBT_{ASTM} , CC_{ASTM} and MCC_{ASTM}) and the other three incorporate modifications proposed by the aforementioned authors ($MBT-EI_{eq}$, CC-f and MCC- a_{eff}).

SERR in Mode II

For Mode II, the standard *ISO 15114* (ISO, 2014) proposes other three methods for the assessment of the fracture energy, which are also used in this research to analyze the data provided by ELS tests: *i. Experimental compliance method (ECM)*, *ii. Simple beam theory (SBT)* and *iii. Corrected beam theory using effective crack length (CBTE)*. The Eqs. 9, 10 and 11 are used to obtain the parameter G_{II} .

$$\text{EMC method} \quad G_{II} = \frac{3P^2 a^2 m}{2b} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where C_0 and m are constants that represent the linear regression of the compliance function related to the crack length a .

$$\text{SBT method} \quad G_{II} = \frac{9P^2 a^2}{4b^2 t_s^3 E_1} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where t_s is the half of the specimen's thickness, L_f is the testing free length and E_1 is the specimen's flexural modulus.

$$\text{CBTE method} \quad G_{II} = \frac{9P^2 a_e^2}{4b^2 t_s^3 E_1} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

where a_e is the effective (calculated) crack length and E_1 is the flexural modulus, which can be deduced from the slope of the clamp calibration data.

The SBT formulation is obtained based on a shear-corrected beam analysis and some researchers have shown that the approach may underestimate the SERR values (Zhang et al., 2010). On the other hand, the EMC method, which can be considered as equivalent to MCC for Mode II, presented similar results provided by finite element models (Zhang et al., 2010). The CBTE method assumes the beam theory, although considering an effective crack length that eliminates the dependency of the measured delamination length, which is often difficult to quantify. Some authors observed that this method might lead to less accurate values for crack initiation due to geometrical characteristics and generated asymmetries in the fracture process (Zhang et al., 2010).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Five DCB and five ELS experiments were performed using specimens extracted from a *DuraSpan* bridge deck system [32]. Throughout this work, the specimens were named as DCB.01 to DCB.05 and ELS.01 to ELS.05. The given pultruded fiber architecture is constituted of rovings and triaxial fabrics, as shown in Figure 1. The measured average fiber volume fractions are presented in Table 1, with their respective standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CoV) indicated in parentheses.

Figure 1. Composite's fiber architecture.

Table 1. Fiber volume fraction.

	$V_{f,total}$ (%)	V_{roving} (%)	V_{fabric} (%)
web	48 ± 1.12 (0.023)	13.5 ± 1.02 (0.076)	34.5 ± 1.24 (0.036)
flange (t = 16.8 mm)	52.3 ± 0.72 (0.014)	23.6 ± 1.82 (0.077)	28.8 ± 2.36 (0.082)
flange (t = 20.3 mm)	52.5 ± 1.68 (0.032)	19.7 ± 1.20 (0.061)	32.8 ± 0.49 (0.015)
flange	52.4 ± 1.21 (0.023)	22.0 ± 2.46 (0.112)	30.4 ± 2.70 (0.089)
flange + roving	50.8 ± 2.44 (0.048)	18.8 ± 4.6 (0.244)	31.9 ± 3.01 (0.094)

The standardized DCB and ELS experiments were adapted to be applied to pultruded specimens. The specimens' dimensions are shown in Table 2 and the used test fixtures are presented in Figure 2. Due to the manufacturing through the pultrusion process of these composites – which precludes the standards recommendations of an initial delamination insertion during fabrication –, a pre-crack with 1-mm of thickness was introduced via a water jet machine.

Table 2. Specimens' dimensions

<i>Experiment</i>	<i>L (mm)</i>	<i>b (mm)</i>	<i>t (mm)</i>	<i>Pre-crack length (mm)</i>
DCB	250	23 ± 0.90	15.5 ± 0.44	60
ELS	310	25 ± 0.03	16.0 ± 0.03	100

Both experiments were conducted under displacement control at a rate of 1mm/min. The DCB experiments were examined on a servo-hydraulic universal testing machine *Walter + Bai* with a load capacity of 40 kN. On the other hand, the ELS experiments were conducted on a table machine *Walter + Bai* with a load capacity of 50 kN. The video-extensometer technique was used to measure the crack lengths. Photos were taken every three seconds using a *Progressive Scan IT CCD* and an *XCG-5005E* camera with a resolution of 2448 x 2048 pixels and an acquisition frequency of 1 Hz. For each registered picture, the corresponding load and displacement increments were recorded, whereas the respective CODs were measured at the first pair of black targets ahead the initial separation.

Figure 2. Test fixtures

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Mode I

All DCB specimens experienced interlaminar failure at their midplane between the two adjacent multiply fabrics layers, as presented in Figure 3. The crack propagation typically followed the fiber architecture configuration, until reaching in average approximately 108 mm of total crack length and 11.1 mm of crack opening displacement (COD).

Figure 3. Failure mode of DCB specimens: (a) DCB.01; (b) DCB.02; (c) DCB.03; (d) DCB.04; (e) DCB.05.

The presence of fiber bridging was observed in all specimens, to lesser or greater extent. The specimen DCB.05 was, clearly, the one that least presented the development of such mechanism, whereas in DCB.01, it was possible to visually notice a large fiber amount crossing the crack along the crack length. The load P vs. displacement δ curves of all five specimens are presented in Figure 4. It can be observed that all specimens have shown a very similar behavior in terms of both curves.

A comparison between the six methods applied in DCB.04 experiment can be seen through Figure 4. The initiation values $G_{I,tip}$ were attributed to the point where the cracks could be visually identified. Table 3 shows the average SERR for both crack initiation and propagation for each one of the six data reduction methods. As can be seen, five methods (MBT_{ASTM} , MCC_{ASTM} , $MBT-EI_{eq}$, $CC-f$ and $MCC-a_{eff}$) presented very similar R-curves. With exception of the CC_{ASTM} , in all methods it is possible to identify a typical curve for specimens experiencing delamination growth with the presence of fiber bridging, in which the energy release rate increase is noticeable up to a maximum level, reaching the steady-state SERR value, characterized by a well-defined plateau that corresponds to the full development of fiber bridging mechanism. On the other hand, for CC_{ASTM} method, it was observed a clear downward tendency in SERR values the plateau region. This behavior was observed for all specimens when using the given methods. In general, a high scattering was observed for the SERR values for crack initiation, whereas very similar average values were found for the crack propagation SERR obtained by the other five methods, with differences lower than 4%.

Figure 4. Experimental results for Mode I

Table 3. Average experimental results for Mode I.

<i>Experimental methods</i>	EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS	
	<i>Average G_I (J/m²)</i>	
	For crack initiation <i>($G_{I,tip}$)</i>	For crack propagation <i>($G_{I,tot}$)</i>
MBT_{ASTM}	661 ± 181	1,300 ± 93
$MBT-EI_{eq}$	520 ± 159	1,337 ± 97
CC_{ASTM}	963 ± 254	1,175 ± 88
$CC-f$	465 ± 151	1,352 ± 94
MCC_{ASTM}	615 ± 171	1,323 ± 92
$MCC-a_{eff}$	513 ± 143	1,337 ± 93

The starting point of the plateau in R-curves indicates that the fiber bridging mechanism is fully developed and allows to identify the fiber bridging length. The average value of the opening crack for a fully developed fiber bridging was 0.49 mm and this information is relevant to determine the cohesive law used in FEM models. The DCB.01 presented the largest values of fiber bridging lengths and its behavior might be compared to a large-scale bridging, since the specimen's thickness is close to 16 mm.

In opposition, DCB.02 and DCB.03 presented approximately only 7 mm and 9 mm of fiber bridging length, respectively.

Mode II

The interlaminar failure in ELS specimens occurred, in some cases, between two adjacent fabric layers while in other cases, the crack occurred between fabric and roving layers, as shown in Figure 5. The grooves observed on the specimens' lateral sides were generated by the cutting process with the water jet machine and it was not possible to remove them via manual polishing. In general, all specimens experienced a fast delamination growth after crack initiation, with abrupt and high increases in crack length, among which some can be identified in P vs. δ curves, shown in Figure 6a, through sudden drops of the load. All specimens presented similar initial stiffness, with maximum loads varying from 550.3 N to 603.0 N.

The average SERR values for Mode II were obtained from EMC, SBT and CBTE methods and are presented in Table 4. The generated R-curves for each method are shown in Figure 6a. Most of specimens experienced an increase of $G_{II, tot}$ until the end, without a well-defined plateau. This indicates a possible fiber bridging not yet fully developed, which is difficult to confirm visually during the experiment due the mode of loading. As observed for DCB, a high scattering was observed for the SERR for crack initiation, whereas for crack propagation CBTE and SBT presented very close results between each other, with differences lower than 1%. The SBT, on the other hand, presented the most deviating results.

Figure 5. Failure mode of ELS specimens: (a) ELS.01; (b) ELS.02; (c) ELS.03; (d) ELS.04; (e) ELS.05.

Figure 6. Experimental results for Mode II.

Table 4. Average experimental results for Mode II.

<i>Experimental methods</i>	EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS	
	<i>Average G_{II} (J/m²)</i>	
	For crack initiation <i>($G_{II,tip}$)</i>	For crack propagation <i>($G_{II,tot}$)</i>
<i>CBTE</i>	522 ± 340	2,124 ± 291
<i>SBT</i>	312 ± 226	1,177 ± 184
<i>EMC</i>	568 ± 442	2,104 ± 307

CONCLUSIONS

This work aims to bring clarity about the application of standardized methods for the determination of Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture parameters in pultruded specimens where it is not applicable to insert a thin pre-crack during fabrication. An experimental investigation was conducted on DCB and ELS and the outcomes of various data reduction methods were compared. Among the six methods used for mode I, the CC_{ASTM} was the only one that presented a non-typical R-curve behavior with a clear downward tendency in the plateau region. This response could possibly be caused by the absence of the parameter Δ in the formulation. The other five methods used for Mode I presented very similar results in terms of SERR for crack propagation, with differences lower than 3.8% between each other. For mode II, the SBT method presented critical energy release rates lower than the values found for Mode I, which is unusual. On the other hand, CBTE and EMC methods provided very similar SERR values, both for crack initiation and propagation, with differences lower than 8% and 1%, respectively, between each other.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior – Brasil (CAPES) – Finance Code 001 –, the internationalization program CAPES PrInt – number of process 88887.363677/2019-00 and the support of this work by the *Composite Construction Laboratory* (CCLab) at the *École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne* (EPFL) and the manufacturer of the bridge deck systems Martin Marietta Composites Inc. in Raleigh (United States).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is found in its entirety in (Cintra, 2023).